

DEVELOPMENT OF A STRATEGY TO INCREASE THE COMPETITIVENESS OF A CONSTRUCTION ORGANIZATION*Leshchynsky V.**Doctor of Law,**Associate Professor of the Department of Agricultural Economics and Management**Kyiv Agrarian University**National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine**Kyiv***Abstract**

This article examines the development of strategies for improving the competitiveness of construction companies. The main types of strategies are identified and the advantages and disadvantages of each group are highlighted. The article also focuses on the specific characteristics of the construction industry and the specific activities of construction companies.

Keywords: competitiveness, construction companies, strategy.

The competitive advantages of construction products have a defined life cycle and are subject to limitations, limiting the long-term growth of a construction organization's competitiveness. From this perspective, methodological approaches to increasing the competitiveness of construction organizations objectively require a combination of different types of competitive strategies. This is entirely possible within a single construction organization, but in some cases, it is more effective when searching for an optimal competitiveness growth strategy [1].

Firstly, this is required by the market and competitive environment, which place high demands on the quality of manufactured products, which presupposes high technical and technological readiness of construction organizations to create innovative construction products.

Secondly, modern construction methods based on the concept of innovative development, including the use of flexible production schemes and technologies and the formation of independent working groups, enable the integration of various strategies. Furthermore, a well-founded choice of a strategy for increasing the competitiveness of a construction organization allows for the realization of synergies and the resulting additional benefits. Based on the conducted research into the conditions and factors for enhancing competitive advantage, it is possible to identify three main areas or strategies for enhancing the competitiveness of a construction organization. The first area is related to minimizing production costs. A cost leadership strategy is a strategy for creating sustainable competitive advantages for construction organizations by achieving relatively low production costs and thereby capturing a larger market share. The second area of competitive strategy development is related to the implementation of highly specialized innovative production. When choosing a specialization strategy, a construction organization must have a system for ensuring high-quality production and a developed marketing system in order to win consumer preferences and strengthen its market niche.

The third area of developing an optimal competitive strategy for a construction organization is associated with concentrating efforts on a specific market

segment. In this case, the focusing strategy is associated with narrow specialization, which allows for the achievement of competitive advantages by fully satisfying the needs of target clients. Within the framework of these areas, it is possible to develop various types of strategies for enhancing the competitiveness of construction organizations. In the literature [5,7], the following four strategic alternatives are commonly identified: concentrated growth, integrated growth, diversified growth, and downsizing. When considering concentrated growth strategies, it should be noted that these strategies involve modifying two elements: the product and/or the market. When choosing these strategies, manufacturers attempt to improve quality or introduce new products within the industry.

At the same time, construction companies continue to explore possible ways to improve their position in established markets or attempt to focus their efforts on developing emerging markets or market segments. Experience shows that a concentrated growth strategy is typical for construction companies characterized by relatively stable production technologies; their development goals are set based on the achieved level and adjusted according to changing external and internal conditions.

Those who adhere to an integrated growth strategy typically strive to diversify their activities in order to exit stagnant markets. Since stagnation typically leads to bankruptcy in virtually any industry, managers strive to significantly increase annual production growth rates compared to previous periods. Moreover, both internal and external factors can contribute to this growth. For example, internal growth can occur through expanding the product range. External - operate in related industries through horizontal/vertical integration, for example, through the acquisition/absorption of another company or the merger of several firms, etc.

Such integrated growth is recommended in situations where a construction organization has a strong market position or can gain additional benefits from repositioning while remaining within the industry framework. In this case, the following competitiveness growth strategies are possible:

- regressive integration, which consists of the construction organization's attempt to subordinate and/or

control its suppliers;

- progressive integration, which involves the construction organization's attempt to acquire and/or control resource distribution systems;
- horizontal integration, which is expressed by the construction organization's attempt to acquire/control competing companies.

When the growth and development reserves in a particular industry market with a given product have been exhausted, a diversified growth strategy is adopted. The main factors that determine the choice of this strategy are the saturation of the market with a certain type of product/service for various reasons, the availability of free funds that can be profitably invested in other areas of activity, changes in fiscal policy associated with a reduction in tax payments, relaxations in customs policy, and a number of others.

Diversified growth strategies typically include:

1. A concentric diversification strategy, based on the production of new products based on existing production.
2. A horizontal diversification strategy, which involves developing technologically unrelated products/services that leverage the existing capabilities of the construction organization and target specific customers.
3. A conglomerate diversification strategy, which involves the structural expansion of the construction organization by developing the production of technologically unrelated products/services, intended for sale in new markets. In our opinion, this is one of the most challenging competitive growth strategies for construction organizations.

A diversified growth strategy is appropriate in cases where the industry has exhausted its potential to create favorable opportunities for further development, or, in other words, where the potential for growth outside the industry is significantly more attractive. Finally, a degrowth strategy is appropriate in situations where restructuring is necessary, either as a result of a prolonged period of growth or to improve efficiency during periods of stagnation. This strategy is aimed at a systematic and targeted reduction in production.

Degrowth strategies typically include:

1. A liquidation strategy, which is one of the most rigorous degrowth strategies. It is applicable when continued production is no longer feasible.
2. A quick-success strategy [3], which involves maximizing total revenue in the short term. It may involve maximizing income from the sale of company assets.
3. A cost-cutting strategy associated with the liquidation of several company divisions as a result of a change in the business model.

It should be noted that different strategies for improving the competitiveness of a construction organization can be applied in different situations:

- at the start-up stage of entrepreneurial activity;
- at a specialized enterprise (single-product);
- in a diversified enterprise, where the overall development strategy of the enterprise can be supported by a growth strategy for individual product lines.

Due to these circumstances, construction organizations may offer a wide range of strategic alternatives for increasing competitiveness. However, the choice of the most preferable strategy for increasing a construction organization's competitiveness directly depends on its current situation in the competitive market.

Therefore, we believe it would be appropriate to propose some general approaches to the process of selecting and developing strategies for increasing the competitiveness of a construction organization based on a correlation between the development prospects of economic entities in the construction industry, their priorities in upgrading their material and technical base, and the efficient use of various types of resources.

Fulfilling these conditions requires developing a mechanism for selecting strategies for increasing the competitiveness of construction organizations that are most preferable and appropriate for the innovative stage of the industry's development in an environment of intensifying competition.

Thus, if the basic strategies reflect four different approaches to the development of a construction organization, related to changes in the state of one and/or several elements, such as: product; market; technology; If the industry is in a competitive market, the combination of the alternatives considered represents a combined strategy for increasing product competitiveness.

A combined strategy is typically pursued by construction companies with competitive potential and producing competitive products.

The individualization of customer demand for construction products is driving the intensification of specialization processes among construction companies and the actualization of market segmentation activities. Since the current construction market is characterized by increasingly personalized demand, a strategy of rational specialization in construction production offers significant advantages over other strategies. It enables a more accurate and differentiated understanding of the market situation; it contributes to improved customer service through positioning and understanding of specific customer needs; and it creates opportunities for the effective allocation of marketing budgets in accordance with the current requirements of the construction market.

Based on this position, a strategy for rational production specialization has been developed. This strategy enhances the competitiveness of construction organizations by satisfying individualized demand in a competitive market, creating sustainable competitive advantages, and rationally utilizing the resource and innovative potential of the construction organization.

A strategy for rational production specialization enables construction organizations to achieve a high market share in their target segment. Rather than simply being an extension of an innovation strategy, a strategy for rational specialization is a tool in a construction organization's competitive policy aimed at eliminating ineffective mechanisms that hinder competitive growth and innovative development.

The potential of this strategy for construction organizations lies in the ability to quickly and effectively differentiate their products in accordance with the individual needs of customers. The most typical application

of a strategy for rational production specialization is focusing efforts on the most complete and high-quality satisfaction of customers' growing, personalized needs. Thus, the key idea of a rational production specialization strategy is that a construction organization plans its activities based on the needs of customers in a specific market segment—that is, not on the overall needs of the construction market as a whole, but on the effective demand of specific customers and clients.

It is important to note the importance of satisfying the above-mentioned construction market segmentation criteria with specific requirements. This means:

- measuring them during the development and implementation of construction market research;
- reflecting the differentiation of construction organizations' customers based on the most significant segmentation criteria;
- identifying differences in market structure in order to more accurately define the boundaries of specific construction market segments.

A rational production specialization strategy focuses efforts on satisfying the needs of a specific market segment or a specific consumer group, without aiming to cover the entire market. The objective is to meet these needs better than the competitor. This strategy may include elements of strategies such as differentiation and cost leadership, or rely on both simultaneously, but only within the target segment.

A rational specialization strategy can be based on existing growth strategies [6]. The conceptual idea behind a rational production specialization strategy is the recognition that a construction organization's positioning in a target market segment is analogous to the individuality of its products and manufacturer.

From this perspective, we share the hypothesis [4, 7], which states that "competitiveness is not an advantage over competitors, but an advantage relative to consumers." Positioning construction products, as a search for the most attractive market position in a target market segment, is a process of ensuring the construction organization's greatest consumer preferences.

In this case, it is customary to distinguish between actual and estimated positioning. In actual positioning, through retrospective analysis and research into volume indicators, market share, and market segments, a construction organization can assess the position of its products in the market, as well as its overall market potential. The smaller the difference between estimated and actual positioning, the more reliable the forecast for growth in the competitiveness of construction products, taking into account effective demand.

Focusing on existing problems and developing a strategy for achieving estimated (desired) positions, it should be noted that the effectiveness of this solution depends on the correct choice of the current position, as well as the directions for its development. Several key strategic alternatives are possible, namely: strengthening existing positions, gradual or radical changes in positions (or repositioning), and displacing direct competitors from their positions. When choosing forms and methods for managing the competitiveness of a construction organization, the following applied recommendations should be followed:

- positioning should be based on the consumer benefits of the products offered (e.g., environmentally friendly and safe areas for development);
- positioning based on the prestige of the product (offering luxury housing);
- positioning by expanding the range or attracting potential buyers of a certain type of construction product (the possibility of obtaining housing with installment payments);
- positioning taking into account the strengths and weaknesses of direct competitors.

Strategic positioning of construction products in a selected target segment leads to an increase in the production of differentiated products designed and manufactured for various consumer groups, which, in turn, leads to the need for constant updating or improvement of manufactured products, and predetermines the search for and development of new technical solutions.

References

1. Lych, V. and Kutsenko, A. (2022), "Essential characteristic of the competitiveness of a construction enterprise", *Prostorovyi rozvytok*, no. 2, pp. 144-159.
2. Kramar, O.M. (2019), "Peculiarities of the impact of personnel provision on the results of the functioning of construction enterprises", *Naukovi zapysky Lvivskoho universytetu biznesu ta prava. Seriya ekonomichna. Seriya yurydychna*, Iss. 23, pp. 42-47.
3. Pryhodko O., Kushnir I., Hrynenko I., Khomenko O. Innovative analytical and applied apparatus for modeling the organization of construction and development support of projects. International independent scientific journal. 2021. №34 (2). p.6- 11. ISSN 3547-2340 (Kraków, Rzeczpospolita Polska). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7061509>
4. Ryzhakova G. M. General-methodical regulation and analytical and information support of administration processes in the modern system of building development. Modern problems of architecture and urban planning. 2019. №55, C.154–168.
5. Kucherenko O., Ryzhakova, G., Chupryna K., Shpakova H., Kishchak N. Veremeev S. Scientific and applied components of the formation of the strategy of institutional-oriented diversification of construction enterprises. Management of development of complex systems. 2021. №47. C.109–118; [dx.doi.org/10.32347/2412-9933.2021.47.109-118](https://doi.org/10.32347/2412-9933.2021.47.109-118).
6. Malikhina O. M. Methodological regulation and analytical and information support of the management of organizations in the modern system of construction. Formation of market relations in Ukraine. 2021. №7–8. C.59–65.
7. Chernyshev D., Ryzhakova G., Honcharenko T., Petrenko H., Chupryna I., Reznik N. Digital Administration of the Project Based on the Concept of Smart Construction. In: Alareeni, B., Hamdan, A. (eds) Explore Business, Technology Opportunities and Challenges. After the Covid-19 Pandemic. ICBT 2022. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems. Springer, Cham. 2023. № 495. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-08954-1_114.